

**REMEDIAL MEASURES FOR IMPROVING THE READING ABILITY OF THE
STUDENTS**

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Introduction

Education shapes the personality of the individual. A schools and colleges social institution takes the responsibility of shaping the pupil. The school is expected to teach the three R's to the students. i.e. Reading, Writing and Reckoning. When student completes the school course, he or she expected to have mastery over three skills-Reading, Writing, counting and computations. Of these, the present research study is related to reading. It has found that the Highschool students do react fluently, with proper pronunciations but they seem to understand very little what they have read. The present research study was needed to improve student's habits of silent reading. It was also necessary for developing the habits of extensive reading or skimming, and the intensive reading or scanning. It is evident that skimming and scanning lead to comprehension of the reading material. Thus, the present research study was necessary to improve reading ability of students.

Significance of the Research Study

The students selected are the real beneficiaries of this research study. The different strategies that have been evolved will be beneficial to the students especially that of improving the reading ability of the students. Remedial measures were used for them. They were provided with practice in skimming and scanning and their progress in reading has improved notably. Thus, the present research was significant to those students.

Research Problem

Remedial Measures for Improving the Reading Ability of Students

Statement of the Research Study

A Study of Remedial Measures for Improving the Reading Ability of Std. VI Students for Improving the Effectiveness of those Measures.

Definitions of Terms

Reading: Grasping of the English language patterns from its written patterns.

Skimming: An ability to run one's eye quickly through reading material for ascertaining the gist, central idea or the overall information.

Scanning: An ability to get a particular bit of information through reading.

Objectives of the Research Study

1. To identify the students who are poor in the skimming and scanning abilities
2. To develop remedial measures for improving the skimming and scanning abilities.
3. To utilize the remedial measures for the students of sample.
4. To verify the effectiveness of the measures.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pretest and post test by the students in skimming abilities.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pretest and posttest by the students in scanning abilities.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pretest and posttest by the students in reading ability.

Methodology of the Research Study

For the present research study, the descriptive cum experimental method was used. In order to procure support material about the students progress in the skimming and the scanning abilities, to select student sample and to verify the effectiveness of the remedial measures, the descriptive method was used.

In order to improve the skimming and the scanning abilities of underachievers, remedial measures were to be applied and the effectiveness of those measures had to be verified. For this purpose, the experimental method was used.

Design of the Research Study

The One-Group, Pre test-Post test design of the Experimental Research was used.

O1 X O2

O1: Pre test

O2: Post test

Variables

Independent Variable: Remedial Measures applied by Researcher

Dependent Variable: Improvement in the Reading Ability

Sample of the research Study

Researcher first of all observed the students who displayed underdeveloped progress in the reading ability especially in the sub skills- skimming and scanning. Identified 23 students. Since the observations were casual and rather unsystematic, a proper pretest was administered to them. On the basis of the scores 20 students were selected for remedial treatment. That group was the sample of the study. The same students were supplied with post test.

Tools used for research Study

Researcher used the teacher-made test as a tool for procuring the support material. The present study is related to reading ability that was fixed for skimming and scanning. Therefore it was decided to develop a test consisting of two sub-tests.viz. a test for testing the skimming ability of 10 Marks and the other for testing the scanning ability of 15 Marks.

Procedure of the Research Study

Students with a poor progress in the reading ability were identified through observations.

There were three main stages in the procedure-

1. Pre-testing stage
2. Training stage
3. Post-testing Stage

Statistical Techniques used for analysis of Data

1. Mean
2. Standard Deviation
3. t-value

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis-1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pretest and post test by the students in skimming abilities.

No. of Students	Tests	Mean	S.D.	t-Value	Level of Significance
20	Pre test	2.3	0.979	14.94	0.01
	Post test	6.2	1.581		

At df =18, the table t-value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.88 and the calculated t-value is 14.94. Calculated t-value 14.94 is greater than 2.88, hence it is significant. Therefore hypothesis-1 is rejected. Hence it was inferred that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in the pre test and post test by the student in skimming abilities.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pretest and posttest by the students in scanning abilities.

No. of Students	Tests	Mean	S.D.	t-Value	Level of Significance
20	Pre test	4.3	1.326	9.134	0.01 Significant
	Post test	9.5	1.549		

At $df= 18$, the table t-value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.88 and the calculated t-value is 9.134. The calculated t-value 9.134 is greater than table t-value, hence it is significant. Therefore the hypothesis-2 is rejected. Hence it was inferred that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in the pre test and post test by the student in scanning abilities.

Hypothesis-3: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pretest and posttest by the students in reading ability.

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No. of Students	Tests	Mean	S.D.	t-Value	Level of Significance
20	Pre test	6.5	1.94	29.19	0.01 Significant
	Post test	15.7	15.7		

At $df= 18$, the table t-value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.88 and the calculated t-value is 29.19. The calculated t-value 29.19 is greater than table t-value, hence it is significant. Therefore the hypothesis-3 is rejected. Hence it was inferred that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in the pre test and post test by the student in reading ability.

Findings of the Research Study

1. There is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pre test and post test by the students in the skimming abilities.
2. There is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pre test and post test by the students in the scanning abilities.
3. There is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores obtained in pre test and post test by the students in the reading ability.

Educational Implications of the Research Study

The English language teachers should realize the value of the students reading ability and try to improve it. Teacher should utilize the introduction stage to recall the previous knowledge and the presentation, recapitulation and application stages for skimming and scanning. The English language teachers should also improve the reading ability of the students in every period and that too, regularly.

References

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